

THERAPEUTIC OUTCOMES IN TUBERCULOSIS PATIENTS WITH MULTIDRUG-RESISTANCE

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ABSTRACT

Multidrug-resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB) is the biggest health concerns in the world today, due to its restricted and expensive treatment options. The severity and burden of MDR-TB differ significantly from nation to nation & region to region. According to the World Health Organisation (WHO) most recent study, there are approximately 4,50,000 MDR-TB cases worldwide, with the majority occurring in China, India, Eastern Europeans and Central Asian Countries. MDR-TB is tuberculosis which is resistant to atleast isoniazid & rifampicin, the two most potent anti-TB drugs. Using second line medications, MDR-TB can be managed and cured. However, there are few choices for second line therapy, and requires prolonged chemotherapy (lasting at least 9 months & sometimes up to 20 months), using pricey and toxic drugs. The treatment is challenging for MDR-TB, as it requires administration of at least four antitubercular medications, many of which are held with frequent adverse reactions. Drugs should be selected based on the past medication history, known resistance patterns, and drug-susceptibility testing (DST) data, if available.

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INTRODUCTION

Tuberculosis (TB) continues to be the most lethal infectious worldwide. The bacteria that cause tuberculosis can become resistant to the antimicrobial medications used to treat the condition. MDR-TB is a type of tuberculosis brought on by infectious agents that are resistant to rifampicin and isoniazid, the two most potent first-line TB medications. Second-line medications can be utilized to control and even eradicate MDR-TB. However, second-line treatment choices are few and call for lengthy chemotherapy (lasting at least 9 months and possibly 20 months) with expensive and hazardous drugs. Treatment for MDR-TB can be tricky because at least four antitubercular drugs must be administered, many of which have regular adverse effects. Drug sensitive tuberculosis is defined as tuberculosis, infected with *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (MTB) sensitive to all first line drugs. Rifampicin-resistance tuberculosis is now treated as multidrug-resistant TB (MDR-TB), as that World Health Organisation (WHO) 2016 MDR-TB guidelines update. Isoniazide-monoresistant tuberculosis; the guidelines have recently been reviewed and revised. Polyresistant tuberculosis; is referred as multiple resistance but that do not meet the criteria for MDR-TB, i.e., resistance to isoniazid, streptomycin, ethambutol & pyrazinamide.

MDR-TB, or multidrug-resistant tuberculosis, continues to be a public health emergency and a security risk to health. In 2020, 150 359 individuals were receiving treatment for MDR/RR-TB worldwide, a 15% decrease from 177 100 in 2019. Adults made up the majority of those seeking therapy.

DRUG REGIMEN FOR MDR-TB:

Drug classification for MDR-TB by World Health Organisation (WHO).

Groups	Steps	Medicines
Group A	Include all 3 drugs	Levofloxacin (or) Moxifloxacin Bedaquiline Linezolid
Group B	Add one or two drugs	Clofazimine Cycloserine (or) Terizidone
Group C	Add to complete regimen & when medicines from groups A and B can't be used	Ethambutol Deleamanid Pyrazinamide Imipenem-cilastatin (or) meropenem Amikacin (or streptomycin) Ethionamide (or) prothionamide Para-aminosalicylic acid

DISCUSSION

STUDY 01: Christina Maier et al., (2023): Conducted a study on 163 patients with MDR/RR-TB treatment based on drug susceptible testing (DST). 15 of the 163 (9.2%) *M. tuberculosis* isolates tested positive for additional resistance to fluoroquinolones or second-line injectable drugs (amikacin, capreomycin, and/or kanamycin) during phenotypic testing. 29 of the 163 (17.8%) *M. tuberculosis* strains showed resistance to both drug groups. (Extensively drug-resistant tuberculosis, according to a former definition). Treatment for MDR/RR-TB lasted 20 months on average (interquartile range: 19.3-21.6 months), using five active medications on average. The average follow-up period was four years. (47.7 months; interquartile range, 21.7–65.8 months). According to the outcome criteria of WHO-2013, WHO-2021, and the Tuberculosis Network European Trials Group-2016, 25 (15.3%), 82 (50.3%), and 95 (58.3%) of the 163 patients were cured, respectively. 17.4 out of 163 people were lost to follow-up, or 10.4%. HIV-positive patients had a higher risk of dying (hazard ratio, 4.28; 95% CI, 1.26-12.86); as did elderly patients (hazard ratio, 1.08; 95% CI, 1.05-1.12; increment of 1 year). Overall, 101/122 (82.8%) patients with a known status (not lost) and a long-term, relapse-free cure out of 163 patients encountered this.

STUDY 02: Kakchapati et al., (2021): Conducted a study out of 494 MDR-TB cases, 17 had lost treatment records, so the remaining 477 cases were included in the analysis. The cases observed in males were 65% and 35% in females. MDR-TB treatment outcomes consists of 43% ongoing treatment, 32% finished their treatment, 13% were defaulted, 7% deaths, and 3% treatment failure. As per the study, the younger age groups are more susceptible for drug resistance and 43% of patients had stopped treatment before the course of treatment as the treatment requires 18 to 24 months lead to low cure rate. Any treatment advantage, according to the survival analysis, was limited to the first 24 months.

STUDY 03: Tim Cutfield et al., (2021): Conducted a study on 60 MDR-TB patients, 41 of these received anti-TB treatment in the past. The average duration of treatment was 22 months. About 93% (38/41) of patients with MDR-TB treatment were initiated, three patients (7%) were transferred out, and four patients (10%) were undergoing MDR-TB treatment. Six months duration of amikacin treatment was ongoing at the time of review. In all, 38 patients treated with MDR-TB treatment exhibited at least one documented adverse effect. Common adverse effects include 66% gastrointestinal, 50% neurologic, 47% ototoxicity, and 37% psychiatric. The end of the study describes 95% (18/19) of patients had completed their MDR-TB treatment.

STUDY 04: Kefyalew Addis Alene et al., (2017): Conducted a study on 282 patients with MDR-TB treatment, of which 242 patients had complete record. Out of 242 MDR-TB patients, 131 (54%) patients were cured, 23 (10%) had fully completed their treatment, 31 (13%) died and 4 (2%) encountered treatment failure. Among these 154 patients, 53 (22%) patients were not evaluated for the treatment outcome, because 20 (8%) of them were still receiving treatment, 27 (11%) had been lost to follow-up, 6 (2%) transferred to another MDR-TB treatment centre. At the end of 6 months the overall cumulative probability of survival was 86% (95% CI: 85.9%, 92.9%) and for 24 months it was 80% (95% CI: 70.1%, 87%). This important finding in the study was, during the intensive phase (the first 6 months of MDR-TB) both the poor treatment outcomes & loss to follow-up occurred. Thus, this study demonstrates the good treatment outcomes in MDR-TB patients of resource-limited and TB endemic nation.

STUDY 05: Alene et al., (2017): Conducted a study on bacteriologically confirmed 408 MDR-TB patients were admitted to MDR-TB treatment centre. Based on the DST results and previous history of TB treatment, the patients were treated with an individualised therapeutic/treatment regimen containing four drugs. Injectable agent, a fluoroquinolone, ethambutol, pyrazinamide, clarithromycin, para-amino salicylic acid, protonamide, cycloserine are included in the treatment regimen. The duration of hospital stay was 23 days. In MDR-TB patients the treatment duration is of 24 months, where the injectable drugs are practiced for 6 months. The study observed that loss of follow-up was over one quarter of the patients who were initiated with treatment regimen. At the end of the study, 58% of the patients had successful treatment outcomes. However, the study provides evidence treatment success rates over time.

STUDY 06: Tierney et al., (2016): Conducted a study on During the study a total of 90 adolescent patients aging between 10-19 years started their first MDR-TB treatment. 58.9% (53) patients were male, and 41.1% (37) were female and one patient (1.7%) had coinfection with HIV. 23 (29.5%) patients were noted with malnutrition, 2 patients (2.5%) with a history of substance abuse, 4 patients (44.2%) with bilateral & cavitary TB disease, 3 patients (3.3%) with extrapulmonary TB, and 3 patients (3.5%) with extensively drug resistant TB, were documented in the medical record at the start of treatment. At the end of the study 68 patients (75.6%) had positive treatment outcomes, 10 (11.1%) of them were died, 3 (3.3%) of them had treatment failure, one (1.1%) was transferred to another healthcare centre. Negative outcomes in 24.4% of adolescents were noticed during MDR-TB treatment.

STUDY 07: Sarah K Brodeet et al., (2015): Conducted on study about 111 patients were diagnosed with MDR-TB, and about 93 were admitted to the inpatient TB ward. In all, 40% of patients were females and 96% were males & most of them are symptomatic. Out of these, 4 patients were resistant to only isoniazid and rifampicin, the remaining 89 patients were resistant to ≥ 3 medications and the duration of hospitalization of these patients was 126 days. The mean of 5.0 ± 1.5 drugs included in regimen in which most common combination involves at least fluoroquinolones, amikacin & clofazimine. At the end of the treatment 84% of patients had successful outcome. Finally, the study indicates that MDR-TB can be controlled by the selection of available anti-TB drugs with correct combinations.

STUDY 08: Olanrewaju et al., (2014): Conducted a study on 162 MDR-TB patients, 65% were male and their average age was 34 years (interquartile range [IQR]: 29 to 42). 28 (17%) patients were co infected with HIV. After initiation of treatment & at the end of intensive phase 24 patients (15%) were died and remaining 138 (85%) were alive and continuing their treatment (also had sputum culture negative). There had been a tendency for people with HIV to have generally worse outcomes, with significance in mortality in first few weeks after initiation of treatment. Thus, the study had recorded no loss of follow-up, thereby favours 'hospitalization' technique for treating MDR-TB patients. However, this may be a result of the program's modest size and its carefully chosen patient group. Given that less than 5% of all estimated MDR-TB patients are presently receiving treatment and the anticipated rise in demand for hospital beds brought on by the implementation of the Xpert MTB-RIF and the rapid rise in MDR-TB case detection, this approach may be difficult to maintain. Although the study recommends using both ambulatory and hospitalized approaches, the latter should only be used for MDR-TB patients who are at a greater risk of unfavourable outcomes.

STUDY 09: Shewade H. et al., (2014): Conducted a study on 74 MDR-TB patients, with average age in years was 32 (± 12) and 46 (62%) were males. A previous history was present in 54 (73%) patients. The test used for diagnosis were LPA and CbNAAT for 63 (84%) and 12 (16%) respectively. Among all 74 patients, 10 patients (13%, 0.95 CI (7%, 23%)) had pre-treatment loss of follow-up, and the remaining 64 patients started treatment. The median (IQR) number of days from diagnosis to the start of therapy was 7 (4, 11), and 80% (47/59) of patients started their treatments within 14 days. In a programmatic setting, pre-treatment loss to follow-up among MDR-TB patients was not significantly different from the national estimate of 18%. 60% pre-diagnosis loss of follow-up among patients with probable MDR-TB, largely contributed by failure to refer DST. In order to reduce pre-treatment loss to follow-up, time to treatment initiation, and guarantee survival for all patients diagnosed with MDR-TB, we need to strengthen counselling and patient tracking mechanisms.

STUDY 10: Stellah G et al., (2013): Conducted a study on 70 patients with MDR-TB treatment. Among them 61 patients were referred and other 9 were excluded based on diagnosis and drug resistant patterns. The median age was 36 years (± 13), and there were 41 (67%) men. A previous history of TB was present in 60 patients (98%); 52 of these patients (87%) had experienced two or more episodes of the infection. In the most recent incident, 45 (or 75%) people experienced a negative outcome that led to the administration of drug susceptibility tests and a diagnosis of MDR-TB. A diagnostic of MDR-TB was made on average 138 days after the collection of the sputum sample (IQR 101–159). Initiating an MDR-TB therapy regimen took on average, 131 days after an MDR-TB diagnosis (IQR 32–233). Following treatment initiation, 54 patients (89%) finished their intensive phase, three (5%) were defaulted, and four patients (7%) were died. Most patients were successful in finishing the intensive stage of inpatient treatment. Almost everyone had medication-related side effects, but few of them were serious or necessitated changing their treatment regimen. This study is required to ascertain the clinical effect of second-line drug susceptibility testing and the viability of alternate treatments to prolonged hospitalization.

STUUDY 11: Doh Hyung Kim et al., (2010): Conducted a study on 1,407 patients with MDR-TB were diagnosed, of whom 75 (5.3%) had XDR-TBre, 159 (11.3%) had pre-XDR-TBo, 117 (8.3%) had pre-XDR-TBs, and 1,056 (75.1%) had the other type of MDR-TB. (Susceptible to both OFX and SLID). The 1,407 research participants had a 45.3% overall treatment success rate, with cure rates of 30.2%, treatment completion rates of 6.6%, and short-term treatment completion rates of 8.5%. Patients with XDR-TBre, XDR-TBor, and XDR-TB (or-re) had respective mean survival times of 61.7, 68, and 72.2 months, which was less than that of patients with non-XDR MDR-TB (89.2 months). To determine the impact of pre-XDR-TB status on outcomes in patients with MDR-TB, outcomes were compared with respect to both the original and revised definitions of XDR-TB. In addition, outcomes were compared among groups of patients with XDR-TBre, pre-XDR-TBo, pre-XDR-TBs, and the other form (OFX-susceptible/SLID-susceptible) of MDR-TB. For MDR-TB patients with the worst outcomes, the updated XDR-TB definition is suitable. Pre-XDR-TBo and pre-XDR-TBs were both separately linked to poor long-term survival in MDR-TB patients. Patients with pre-XDR-TB who were more susceptible to SM had higher survival rates.

CONCLUSION

Despite the global TB incidence gradually declining, MDR/XDR-TB is a rising threat to the security of global health. Based on the above studies, MDR TB is treatable when the right anti-TB medications are combined and administered by a skilled medical professional. The high incidence of unsuccessful treatment outcomes and loss to follow-up should be addressed with strategies. Treatment for MDR-TB has a high incidence of side effects, particularly prolonged intravenous aminoglycoside therapy. It is anticipated that newer regimens will be more tolerable as they are given with the ongoing assistance of the Tuberculosis Clinical Network. Additionally, more work must be done to better assist patients in finishing their treatments and to assess the effects MDR-TB has on them. Continued focus on infrastructure development and resource allocation will be required to control the current epidemic of drug-resistant tuberculosis as new diagnostic tools and antituberculosis medications become available. Long-term, relapse-free cure from MDR/RR-TB is significantly higher under ideal management circumstances using individualized treatment regimens than cure rates as defined by current treatment outcome definitions.

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Conflicts of interest:

The authors confirm that this article's content has no conflicts of interest.

REFERENCES

- Christina Maier, Dumitru Chesov, Dagmar Schaub, Barbara Kalsdorf, Sönke Andres, Inna Friesen, Maja Reimann, Christoph Lange, Long-term treatment outcomes in patients with multidrug-resistant tuberculosis, *Clinical Microbiology and Infection*, 2023, ISSN 1198-743X, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmi.2023.02.013>.
- Kakchapati S, Gyawali BN, Jha RK, Choonpradub C. Treatment Outcome of Multidrug-Resistant Mycobacterium tuberculosis in Nepal. *Asia Pacific Journal of Public Health*. 2012;24(4):631-640. doi:10.1177/1010539511408067
- Cutfield, T., Mowlem, L., Paynter, J., Christmas, T., Harrison, A., Lewis, C., ... Nisbet, M. (2021). *Treatment and outcomes of Multidrug-resistant tuberculosis in Auckland 1995–2018*. *Internal Medicine Journal*.doi:10.1111/imj.15341
- Alene, K. A., Yi, H., Viney, K., McBryde, E. S., Yang, K., Bai, L., ... Xu, Z. (2017). *Treatment outcomes of patients with multidrug-resistant and extensively drug resistant tuberculosis in Hunan Province, China*. *BMC Infectious Diseases*, 17(1). doi:10.1186/s12879-017-2662-8
- Tierney DB, Milstein MB, Manjourides J, Furin JJ, Mitnick CD. Treatment Outcomes for Adolescents with Multidrug-Resistant Tuberculosis in Lima, Peru. *Global Pediatric Health*. 2016;3. doi:10.1177/2333794X16674382
- Tierney DB, Milstein MB, Manjourides J, Furin JJ, Mitnick CD. Treatment Outcomes for Adolescents with Multidrug-Resistant Tuberculosis in Lima, Peru. *Global Pediatric Health*. 2016;3. doi: 10.1177/2333794X16674382
- Sarah K Brode, Robert Varadi, Jane McNamee, Nina Malek, Sharon Stewart, Frances B Jamieson, Monica Avendano, "Multidrug-Resistant Tuberculosis: Treatment and Outcomes of 93 Patients", *Canadian Respiratory Journal*, vol. 22, Article ID 359301, 6 pages, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2015/359301>
- Oladimeji, O., Isaakidis, P., Obasanya, O. J., Eltayeb, O., Khogali, M., V. Kumar, A. M., Hinderaker, S. G., Abdurrahman, S. T., Lawson, L., & Cuevas, L. E. (2014). Intensive-Phase Treatment Outcomes among Hospitalized Multidrug-Resistant Tuberculosis Patients: Results from a Nationwide Cohort in Nigeria. *PLOS ONE*, 9(4), e94393. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0094393>
- Shewade, H., Kokane, A., Singh, A., Verma, M., Parmar, M., Chahar, S., Tiwari, M., Khan, S., Nagar, M., Singh, S., Mehra, P. and Kumar, A. (2017) Treatment Initiation among Patients with Multidrug Resistant Tuberculosis in Bhopal District, India. *Journal of Tuberculosis Research*, 5, 237-242. doi: 10.4236/jtr.2017.54025
- Mpagama, S. G., Heysell, S. K., Ndu silo, N. D., Kumburu, H. H., Lekule, I. A., Kisonga, R. M., Gratz, J., Boeree, M. J., Houpt, E. R., & Kibiki, G. S. (2013). Diagnosis and Interim Treatment Outcomes from the First Cohort of Multidrug-Resistant Tuberculosis Patients in Tanzania. *PLOS ONE*, 8(5), e62034. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0062034>
- Kim, D. H., Kim, H. J., Park, S.-K., Kong, S.-J., Kim, Y. S., Kim, T.-H., ... Shim, T. S. (2010). *Treatment Outcomes and Survival Based on Drug Resistance Patterns in Multidrug-resistant Tuberculosis*. *American Journal of Respiratory and Critical Care Medicine*, 182(1), 113–119. doi:10.1164/rccm.200911-1656oc.
- Prasad, R., Gupta, N., Balasubramanian, V., & Singh, A. (2015). *Multidrug resistant tuberculosis treatment in India*. *Drug Discoveries & Therapeutics*, 9(3), 156–164. doi:10.5582/ddt.2015.01012.
- Opportunities for Optimizing Management of Multidrug-Resistant Tuberculosis (MDR-TB) in Tanzania. *The East African Health Research Journal*, 2(1), 26-28. <https://doi.org/10.24248/EAHRJ-D-16-00357>
- Individualized treatment of multidrug-resistant tuberculosis using therapeutic drug monitoring. *International Journal of Mycobacteriology*, 5, S44-S45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmyco.2016.07.003>
- Maranetra KN. Treatment of multidrug-resistant tuberculosis in Thailand. *Chemotherapy*. 1996;42 Suppl 3:10-5; discussion 30-3. doi: 10.1159/000239508. PMID: 8980862
- Pablos-Mendez A, Gowda DK, Frieden TR. Controlling multidrug-resistant tuberculosis and access to expensive drugs: a rational framework. *Bull World Health Organ*. 2002;80(6):489-95; discussion 495-500. PMID: 12132008; PMCID: PMC2567530
- Lofranco, V., Balanag Jr, V., Raymond, L., Macalalad, N., Golubkov, A., T. Santiago, M. and G. Garfin, A. (2022) Effectiveness and Safety of 9-Month Treatment Regimen for Multidrug-Resistant Tuberculosis in the Philippines. *Journal of Tuberculosis Research*, 10, 75-86. doi: 10.4236/jtr.2022.102006.
- Tupasi, T.E., Garfin, A.M.G., Kurbatova, E.V., et al. (2016) Factors Associated with Loss to Follow up during Treatment for MDR-TB, the Philippines 2012-2014. *Emerging Infectious Diseases*, 22, 491-502. [Doi.org/10.3201/eid2203.151788](https://doi.org/10.3201/eid2203.151788)
- World Health Organization (2017) *Global Tuberculosis Report 2017*. WHO, Geneva. https://www.who.int/tb/publications/global_report/en/
- "Report warns of rise in drug-resistant tuberculosis", 2017, <http://www.cidrap.umn.edu/news-perspective/2017/03/report-warns-rise-drug-resistant-tuberculosis>
- WHO consolidated guidelines on tuberculosis, Module 4: Treatment - drug-resistant tuberculosis treatment. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2020 (<https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240007048>)
- Field SK, Fisher D, Jarand JM, Cowie RL. New treatment options for multidrug-resistant tuberculosis. *Therapeutic Advances in Respiratory Disease*. 2012;6(5):255-268. doi:10.1177/175346581245219Balabanova Y, Radiulyte B, Davidaviciene E, Hooper R, Ignatyeva O, Nikolayevskyy V, Drobniewski FA. Survival of drug resistant tuberculosis patients in Lithuania: retrospective national cohort study. *BMJ Open*. 2011 Nov 28;1(2): e000351. doi: 10.1136/bmjopen-2011-000351. PMID: 22123922; PMCID: PMC3225583
- Wahid A, Ghafoor A, Khan AW, Al-Worafi YM, Latif A, Shahwani NA, Atif M, Saleem F, Ahmad N. Comparative effectiveness of individualized longer and standardized shorter regimens in the treatment of multidrug resistant tuberculosis in a high burden country. *Front Pharmacol*. 2022 Sep 6; 13:973713. doi: 10.3389/fphar.2022.973713. PMID: 36160454; PMCID: PMC9503836.
- Abidi S, Achar J, AssaoNeino MM, Bang D, Benedetti A, Brode S, Campbell JR, Casas EC, Conradie F, Dravniece G, du Cros P, Falzon D, Jaramillo E, Kuaban C, Lan Z, Lange C, Li PZ, Makhmudova M, Maug AKJ, Menzies D, Migliori GB, Miller A,

- Myrzaliev B, Ndjeka N, Noeske J, Parpieva N, Piubello A, Schwoebel V, Sikhondze W, Singla R, Souleymane MB, Trébuq A, Van Deun A, Viney K, Weyer K, Zhang BJ, Ahmad Khan F. Standardised shorter regimens *versus* individualised longer regimens for rifampin- or multidrug-resistant tuberculosis. *Eur Respir J*. 2020 Mar 20;55(3):1901467. doi: 10.1183/13993003.01467-2019. PMID: 31862767.
25. Ahmad N, Javaid A, Basit A, Afridi AK, Khan MA, Ahmad I, Sulaiman SA, Khan AH. Management and treatment outcomes of MDR-TB: results from a setting with high rates of drug resistance. *Int J Tuberc Lung Dis*. 2015 Sep;19(9):1109-14, I-ii. doi: 10.5588/ijtld.15.0167. PMID: 26260834.
26. Atif M, Ahmad W, Ahmad N, Malik I, Sarwar S. Treatment outcomes among multidrug-resistant TB patients in Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur, Pakistan: a retrospective record review. *Trans R Soc Trop Med Hyg*. 2020 Oct 5;114(10):733-741. doi: 10.1093/trstmh/traa040. PMID: 32556195.
27. Khan I, Ahmad N, Khan S, Muhammad S, Ahmad Khan S, Ahmad I, Khan A, Gulalai, Atif M. Evaluation of treatment outcomes and factors associated with unsuccessful outcomes in multidrug resistant tuberculosis patients in Baluchistan province of Pakistan. *J Infect Public Health*. 2019 Nov-Dec;12(6):809-815. doi: 10.1016/j.jiph.2019.04.009. Epub 2019 May 2. PMID: 31056438.
28. Günther, Gunar; Lange, Christoph; Alexandru, Sofia; Altet, Neus; Avsar, Korkut; Bang, Didi; Barbuta, Raisa; Bothamley, Graham; Ciobanu, Ana; Crudu, Valeriu; Danilovits, Manfred; Dedicat, Martin; Duarte, Raquel; Gualano, Gina; Kunst, Heinke; de Lange, Wiel; Leimane, Vaira; Magis-Escurra, Cecile; McLaughlin, Anne-Marie; Muylle, Inge; Polcová, Veronika; Popa, Christina; Rumetshofer, Rudolf; Skrahina, Alena; Solodovnikova, Varvara; Spinu, Victor; Tiberi, Simon; Viikklepp, Piret; van Leth, Frank (2016). *Treatment Outcomes in Multidrug-Resistant Tuberculosis*. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 375(11), 1103–1105. doi:10.1056/NEJMc1603274
29. Marcos A. Espinal, M.D., Dr.P.H., Adalbert Laszlo, Ph.D., Lone Simonsen, Ph.D., FadilaBoualhal, Ph.D., et al., for the World Health Organization–International Union against Tuberculosis and Lung Disease Working Group on Anti-Tuberculosis Drug Resistance Surveillance April 26, 2001 *N Engl J Med* 2001; 344:1294-1303, DOI: 10.1056/NEJM200104263441706

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